

Evaluating the Influence of Digital Marketing on Tourism Purchases Using Soft Computing

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Abstract. The current work inspects the role of digital marketing in shaping consumer behaviour in the tourism sector. Utilizing soft computing techniques such as Fuzzy TOPSIS. Three primary alternatives—Travel Tickets, Local Experience Bookings, and Travel Insurance—were analyzed for their relative importance in consumer decision-making.

The study follows a structured methodology, converting linguistic consumer responses into triangular fuzzy numbers, constructing a fuzzy decision matrix, and applying normalization and weighting techniques to compute Fuzzy Positive Ideal Solutions (FPIS) and Fuzzy Negative Ideal Solutions (FNIS). The closeness coefficient for each alternative was calculated to determine the most influential factor.

The results provide actionable insights for market researchers, emphasizing the need for targeted digital strategies that enhance consumer engagement through personalized experiences, interactive content, and comprehensive spreading of information.

Keywords: Soft Computing, Digital Marketing, Tourism Purchases, Consumer Behavior, Social Media

1 Introduction

Digital marketing has played an immense role in transforming the tourism industry [1] The importance of social media channels, targeted advertising, and artificial intelligence-pivoted pricing strategies for influencing consumer decision-making, from itinerary design to travel service reservations, is well established [2]. The growing connectivity of digital technology in tourism marketing enables it to effectively reach their target audiences, create highly personalized recommendations, and increase direct engagement with consumers ([3]). Nevertheless, the impact of digital marketing is not uniform among tourism purchases, and evaluation needs structured data-driven measurement approaches.

This research has utilized soft computing (Fuzzy TOPSIS) approach to assess the influence of digital marketing on consumer preferences in tourism. In contrast to conventional evaluation approaches that are primarily based on qualitative specifications, soft computing offers a systematic number-based arrangement to generalize subjective consumer measures. The aim of this study is to rank tourism-related products based on the susceptibility of them being influenced by digital marketing through the review of five critical decision-making criteria that can lead to actionable recommendations for marketers.

It is widely supported that digital marketing is of utmost importance for tourism businesses. Social media marketing[4], interactive advertising, and targeted travel promotions have transformed the ways that consumers find, assess, and acquire travel-related product ([5]). This aspect of the internet has been proven in several studies to impact consumer decision-making behavior when purchasing a product or service, as such elements as interactivity of content, personalization, and accessibility of the information available online seem to affect consumer behaviour ([1]). However, notwithstanding the increasing literature on digital tourism marketing[6], [7], evaluations remain qualitative and largely do not explore consumers' preferences in a quantifiable way.

For example, *Fuzzy TOPSIS*, a soft computing technique, provides a powerful means for handling uncertain and imprecise perceptions of consumers during decision-making [8], [9] in the tourism sector ([10]). Contrary to the traditional decision models, which assume precise numerical inputs for use, soft computing admits linguistic inputs (such as Very influential, Moderately Influential, Less Influential) which have been converted to fuzzy numbers ([11]), making this a perfect mean to translate consumers preferences affected by digital marketing into quantitative inputs.

Airline websites, travel aggregators, and price comparison sites represent the digital marketing platforms that can be part of consumers' decision-making process in an online environment through personalized ads [12], [13], real-time price tracking, and automatic, AI-powered promotions ([14]). *Fuzzy TOPSIS* measures the impact of these strategies, identifying their impact on ticket sales. Online travel agencies (OTAs) and websites such as Airbnb Experiences and Get Your Guide employ social media advertising, influencer partnerships, and user-generated content to attract customers ([3]). This work investigates how online information sufficiency and social media use influence bookings for experiences. Digital insurers employ trust-building strategies, AI recommendations, and comparison websites to sell policies ([1]). This work investigates how comparison websites, social proof, and online advertising influence consumer choice.

2 Materials and Method

The study applies soft computing (*F-TOPSIS*) to evaluate three alternatives: Travel Tickets, Local Experience Bookings, and Travel Insurance with five criteria were used, i.e., Impact of digital marketing and advertising. Ease of product comparison facilitated by social media, Sufficiency of information provided by social media platforms, Interactivity of social media influencing shopping experience, Influence of social media on decision-making.

Data Collection Survey responses were collected from a diverse demographic, focusing on their interaction with digital marketing in the context of tourism purchases. Linguistic terms (e.g., Strongly Agree, Agree, Neutral) were mapped to fuzzy triangular numbers for analysis.

Step 1: Construct the Fuzzy Decision Matrix

The decision matrix is built by mapping survey responses to fuzzy triangular numbers. Each linguistic response (e.g., Strongly Agree, Agree) is transformed into corresponding fuzzy values by using the following scale mentioned in Table 1:

Table 1. Linguistic Scale for Expert Opinion

Linguistic Term	Short Code	Fuzzy Scale (L, M, U)
Very Less Imp.	VLI	(0.0, 0.0, 0.2)
Less Imp.	LI	(0.1, 0.2, 0.3)
Moderately Imp.	MI	(0.3, 0.5, 0.7)
Highly Imp.	HI	(0.6, 0.7, 0.9)
Very Highly Imp.	VHI	(0.8, 1.0, 1.0)

2.1 Materials:

The materials used in the current study are described below:

We considered three crucial alternatives like Travel Tickets, Local Experience Bookings, and Travel Insurance to discuss the effect of digital marketing for tourism purchasing, the three alternatives chosen for analysis represent different aspects of tourism decision-making:

Travel Tickets: This alternative Includes airline, train, and bus ticket bookings influenced by digital platforms and different tourism planner platforms.

Local Experience Bookings: Activities such as guided tours, adventure experiences, and cultural trips which are provided by tour operators and other online platforms.

Travel Insurance: It is a popular and crucial risk-management product which is heavily marketed through online comparison platforms and targeted digital ads.

Evaluation Criteria:

The above mentioned alternatives are evaluated based on five key criteria, which influence consumer decision-making through digital platforms:

Impact of Digital Marketing and Advertising: The extent to which online advertisements affect purchasing decisions.

Ease of Product Comparison Facilitated by social media: How efficiently customers can compare different options using digital tools.

Sufficiency of Information Provided by Social Media Platforms: The completeness and accuracy of information available online.

Interactivity of social media Influencing Shopping Experience: The role of interactive content, reviews, and social engagement.

Influence of social media on Decision-Making: The overall effect of digital influence in final purchase decisions.

3. Methods**Methodologies Used:**

Applying *Fuzzy TOPSIS* to compute closeness coefficients and rank alternatives based on digital marketing influence. This method is selected over other soft computing techniques due to its ability to, handle imprecise and subjective consumer preferences effectively.

Fuzzy Numbers-

A fuzzy number [15], [16] is a concept used in fuzzy logic and mathematics to represent uncertainty or imprecision associated with a numerical value. A fuzzy number is essentially a fuzzy subset of a universe of discourse (denoted as X) that possesses two key properties: convexity and normality. One common type of fuzzy number is the triangular fuzzy number. Unlike a regular number, which has a precise value, a fuzzy number allows for a range of possible values with varying degrees of membership. Essentially, it is a fuzzy subset of a larger set, called the universe of discourse [8] (denoted as X), which contains all possible values that the fuzzy number could take. A fuzzy number has two key properties: **convexity** and **normality**. Convexity means that the membership degree of any value within the fuzzy number does not increase once it starts to decrease—essentially, the shape of the fuzzy number forms a smooth curve or slope without any dips or peaks. Normality means that at least one element in the set has a full membership degree of 1, signifying that it is the most representative or central value of the fuzzy number.

Triangular Fuzzy Number

The triangular fuzzy number [15], [16] [17] (TFN) is described and denoted by a triplet $\tilde{A} = (a, b, c)$ and which has its membership degree as shown by

$$\tilde{\mu}_A(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{x-a}{b-a}, & a \leq x \leq b \\ \frac{c-x}{c-b}, & b \leq x \leq c \\ 0 & \text{else where} \end{cases}$$

Figure 1 Triangular Fuzzy Number

The core method of *Fuzzy TOPSIS* involves evaluating the proximity to both the ideal and anti-ideal solutions, defined as follows:

Step 1:

The opinion of k Decision-Makers in linguistic form will be taken and the fuzzy conversion of these opinions and weight of importance about i^{th} alternative corresponding to j^{th} criteria are mentioned as $\tilde{x}_{ij}^k = (\alpha_{ij}^k, \beta_{ij}^k, \gamma_{ij}^k)$ and $\tilde{w}_j^k = (w_{j1}^k, w_{j2}^k, w_{j3}^k)$ respectively, where $i \in \{1,2,3, \dots, m\}$ and $j \in \{1,2,3, \dots, n\}$

Step 2:

The aggregated fuzzy values of i^{th} alternative and concerning j^{th} criteria are given by $\tilde{x}_{ij} = (\alpha_{ij}, \beta_{ij}, \gamma_{ij})$ such that:

$$\alpha_{ij} = \text{Avg}_k \{ \alpha_{ij}^k \}, \quad \beta_{ij} = \text{Avg}_k \{ \beta_{ij}^k \}, \quad \gamma_{ij} = \text{Avg}_k \{ \gamma_{ij}^k \} \tag{1}$$

And the aggregated fuzzy weights of importance are $\tilde{w}_j = (w_{j1}, w_{j2}, w_{j3})$

$$w_{j1} = \text{Avg}_k \{ w_{j1}^k \}, \quad w_{j2} = \text{Avg}_k \{ w_{j2}^k \}, \quad w_{j3} = \text{Avg}_k \{ w_{j3}^k \} \tag{2}$$

Step 3:

As shown below, the fuzzy decision matrix [18] summarizes the aggregate values:

$$\tilde{D} = \begin{matrix} & \begin{matrix} C_1 & C_2 & \dots & C_n \end{matrix} \\ \begin{matrix} A_1 \\ A_2 \\ \dots \\ A_m \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{x}_{11} & \tilde{x}_{12} & \dots & \tilde{x}_{1n} \\ \tilde{x}_{21} & \tilde{x}_{22} & \dots & \tilde{x}_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \tilde{x}_{m1} & \tilde{x}_{m2} & \dots & \tilde{x}_{mn} \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix} \tag{3}$$

And the aggregate fuzzy weights are

$$\tilde{W} = [\tilde{w}_1 \quad \tilde{w}_2 \quad \tilde{w}_3 \quad \dots \quad \tilde{w}_n]$$

In the above matrix each $\tilde{x}_{ij}, \tilde{w}_j \quad \forall i \in \{1,2,3, \dots, m\}$ and $j \in \{1,2,3, \dots, n\}$ are described using linguistic terms and can subsequently be converted into TFNs $\tilde{x}_{ij} = (\alpha_{ij}, \beta_{ij}, \gamma_{ij})$, and $\tilde{w}_j = (w_{j1}, w_{j2}, w_{j3})$

Step 4:

The fuzzy decision matrix, after normalization, is shown as:

$$\tilde{R} = [\tilde{r}_{ij}]_{m \times n}, \text{ where } i \in \{1,2,3, \dots, m\} \text{ and } j \in \{1,2,3, \dots, n\} \tag{4}$$

Where

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \tilde{r}_{ij} &= \left(\frac{\alpha_{ij}}{\gamma_j^+}, \frac{\beta_{ij}}{\gamma_j^+}, \frac{\gamma_{ij}}{\gamma_j^+} \right) && \text{And} \\ \gamma_j^+ &= \max_i (\gamma_{ij}) && \text{(benefit criteria)} \\ \tilde{r}_{ij} &= \left(\frac{\alpha_j^-}{\gamma_{ij}}, \frac{\alpha_j^-}{\beta_{ij}}, \frac{\alpha_j^-}{\alpha_{ij}} \right) && \text{And} \\ \alpha_j^- &= \min_i (\alpha_{ij}) && \text{(cost criteria)} \end{aligned} \right\}$$

the normalized fuzzy numbers lie in the interval [0, 1]

Step 5:

At this stage, the weighted normalized fuzzy matrix \tilde{V} has been obtained through the application of the following procedure:

$$\tilde{V} = [\tilde{v}_{ij}] = [\tilde{r}_{ij} * \tilde{w}_j]_{m \times n}, \text{ where } i \in \{1,2,3, \dots, m\} \text{ and } j \in \{1,2,3, \dots, n\} \tag{5}$$

Step 6:

The ideal solutions, namely the fuzzy positive ideal solution (FPIS) and the fuzzy negative ideal solution (FNIS), are determined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 A^+ &= (\tilde{\vartheta}_1^+, \tilde{\vartheta}_2^+, \dots, \tilde{\vartheta}_n^+) \quad \text{And} \\
 \tilde{\vartheta}_j^+ &= \max_i(\vartheta_{ij3}) \quad i \in \{1,2,3,\dots,m\} \text{ and } j \in \{1,2,3,\dots,n\} \\
 A^- &= (\tilde{\vartheta}_1^-, \tilde{\vartheta}_2^-, \dots, \tilde{\vartheta}_n^-) \quad \text{And} \\
 \tilde{\vartheta}_j^- &= \min_i(\vartheta_{ij1}) \quad i \in \{1,2,3,\dots,m\} \text{ and } j \in \{1,2,3,\dots,n\}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{6}$$

Step 7:

The values d_i^+ And d_i^- can be used to measure how far each weighted normalized fuzzy value is from the fuzzy positive ideal solution (FPIS) and the fuzzy negative ideal solution (FNIS), respectively. These distances are computed using the following formulas:

$$\begin{aligned}
 d_i^+ &= \sum_{j=1}^n d_{\vartheta}(\tilde{\vartheta}_{ij}, \tilde{\vartheta}_j^+) \quad i \in \{1,2,3,\dots,m\} \\
 d_i^- &= \sum_{j=1}^n d_{\vartheta}(\tilde{\vartheta}_{ij}, \tilde{\vartheta}_j^-) \quad i \in \{1,2,3,\dots,m\}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{7}$$

In these equations, $d_{\vartheta}(\tilde{a}, \tilde{b})$ denotes the distance between two triangular fuzzy numbers \tilde{a} and \tilde{b}

Step 8:

The *CCi* (closeness coefficient) reflects the position of actual solution relative to both the (FNIS A^-) and (FPIS A^+)

$$CCi = \frac{d_i^-}{d_i^- + d_i^+}, \quad i \in \{1,2,3,\dots,m\}
 \tag{8}$$

The best-ranked alternative is the one with the maximum closeness coefficient, indicating it lies closest to the FPIS and farthest from the FNIS.

Step 9: The closeness coefficient serves as a basis for ranking the alternatives.

3 Design of the Model

A case study was carried out with the aim of defining the ranks of the key influencers of Digital marketing, in the course of this study, we successfully identified and documented four specific criteria, about which the experts' opinion in linguistic terms are detailed below:

Table 2. Experts' opinion in linguistic terms

	Criteria	Travel Tickets	Local Experience Bookings	Travel Insurance
DM1	Impact of Digital Marketing	MI	LI	HI
	Ease of Comparison	HI	MI	VHI
	Sufficiency of Information	MI	MI	HI

	Interactivity of Social Media	HI	LI	HI
	Influence on Decision-Making	MI	LI	HI
DM2	Impact of Digital Marketing	HI	MI	HI
	Ease of Comparison	VHI	MI	VHI
	Sufficiency of Information	HI	MI	HI
	Interactivity of Social Media	HI	MI	HI
	Influence on Decision-Making	HI	MI	HI

Legend (Linguistic Scale Used):

VLI = Very Less Imp., **LI** = Less Imp., **MI** = Moderately Imp., **HI** = Highly Imp., **VHI** = Very Highly Imp.
 In the following table Table 3. Experts' opinion converted to fuzzy scale by using the scale mentioned in Table 1. All values follow the fuzzy scale for the corresponding linguistic terms. The mapping is accurate based on expert linguistic opinions. The same fuzzy scale is consistently applied across both decision matrices (DM1 & DM2).

Table 3. Fuzzification of linguistic ratings

	Criteria	Travel Tickets	Local Experience Bookings	Travel Insurance
DM1	Impact of Digital Marketing	(0.3, 0.5, 0.7)	(0.1, 0.2, 0.3)	(0.6, 0.7, 0.9)
	Ease of Comparison	(0.6, 0.7, 0.9)	(0.3, 0.5, 0.7)	(0.8, 1.0, 1.0)
	Sufficiency of Information	(0.3, 0.5, 0.7)	(0.3, 0.5, 0.7)	(0.6, 0.7, 0.9)
	Interactivity of Social Media	(0.6, 0.7, 0.9)	(0.1, 0.2, 0.3)	(0.6, 0.7, 0.9)
	Influence on Decision-Making	(0.3, 0.5, 0.7)	(0.1, 0.2, 0.3)	(0.6, 0.7, 0.9)

DM2	Impact of Digital Marketing	(0.6, 0.7, 0.9)	(0.3, 0.5, 0.7)	(0.6, 0.7, 0.9)
	Ease of Comparison	(0.8, 1.0, 1.0)	(0.3, 0.5, 0.7)	(0.8, 1.0, 1.0)
	Sufficiency of Information	(0.6, 0.7, 0.9)	(0.3, 0.5, 0.7)	(0.6, 0.7, 0.9)
	Interactivity of Social Media	(0.6, 0.7, 0.9)	(0.3, 0.5, 0.7)	(0.6, 0.7, 0.9)
	Influence on Decision-Making	(0.6, 0.7, 0.9)	(0.3, 0.5, 0.7)	(0.6, 0.7, 0.9)

The aggregation was performed using the arithmetic mean formula:

$$\tilde{A}_{ij} = \frac{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{(1)} + \tilde{A}_{ij}^{(2)}}{2} \tag{9}$$

Where: $\tilde{A}_{ij}^{(1)}$, $\tilde{A}_{ij}^{(2)}$ represent the fuzzy ratings provided by Expert 1 and 2 and \tilde{A}_{ij} is the aggregated fuzzy rating for alternative 'j' under criteria 'i', this method ensures that subjective evaluations from different experts are merged into a single representative value.

Table 4. Aggregation of fuzzy ratings

Criteria	Travel Tickets	Local Experience Bookings	Travel Insurance
Impact of Digital Marketing	(0.45, 0.6, 0.8)	(0.2, 0.35, 0.5)	(0.6, 0.7, 0.9)
Ease of Comparison	(0.7, 0.85, 0.95)	(0.3, 0.5, 0.7)	(0.8, 1.0, 1.0)
Sufficiency of Information	(0.45, 0.6, 0.8)	(0.3, 0.5, 0.7)	(0.6, 0.7, 0.9)
Interactivity of Social Media	(0.6, 0.7, 0.9)	(0.2, 0.35, 0.5)	(0.6, 0.7, 0.9)
Influence on Decision-Making	(0.45, 0.6, 0.8)	(0.2, 0.35, 0.5)	(0.6, 0.7, 0.9)

Further, the normalization process was performed to get a normalized fuzzy decision matrix which is incorporated in the following table given below:

Table 5. Normalized aggregated fuzzy decision matrix

Criteria	Travel Tickets	Local Experience Bookings	Travel Insurance
Impact of Digital Marketing	(0.500, 0.667, 0.889)	(0.222, 0.389, 0.556)	(0.667, 0.778, 1.000)
Ease of Comparison	(0.875, 0.850, 0.950)	(0.375, 0.500, 0.700)	(1.000, 1.000, 1.000)
Sufficiency of Information	(0.500, 0.667, 0.889)	(0.333, 0.556, 0.778)	(0.667, 0.778, 1.000)
Interactivity of Social Media	(0.667, 0.778, 1.000)	(0.222, 0.389, 0.556)	(0.667, 0.778, 1.000)
Influence on Decision-Making	(0.500, 0.667, 0.889)	(0.222, 0.389, 0.556)	(0.667, 0.778, 1.000)

Pairwise comparison for the criteria to evaluate fuzzy weights

Table 6. Pairwise comparison of fuzzy ratings of criteria

Criteria	Impact of Digital Marketing (L, M, U)	Ease of Comparison (L, M, U)	Sufficiency of Information (L, M, U)	Interactivity of Social Media (L, M, U)	Influence on Decision-Making (L, M, U)
Impact of Digital Marketing	(1.0, 1.0, 1.0)	(0.5, 0.7, 1.0)	(0.4, 0.6, 0.9)	(0.3, 0.5, 0.8)	(0.2, 0.4, 0.7)
Ease of Comparison	(1.0, 1.4, 2.0)	(1.0, 1.0, 1.0)	(0.5, 0.7, 1.0)	(0.4, 0.6, 0.9)	(0.3, 0.5, 0.8)
Sufficiency of Information	(1.1, 1.6, 2.5)	(1.0, 1.4, 2.0)	(1.0, 1.0, 1.0)	(0.5, 0.7, 1.0)	(0.4, 0.6, 0.9)
Interactivity of Social Media	(1.3, 2.0, 3.3)	(1.1, 1.6, 2.5)	(1.0, 1.4, 2.0)	(1.0, 1.0, 1.0)	(0.5, 0.7, 1.0)
Influence on Decision-Making	(1.4, 2.5, 5.0)	(1.3, 2.0, 3.3)	(1.1, 1.6, 2.5)	(1.0, 1.4, 2.0)	(1.0, 1.0, 1.0)

If multiple experts provide input, their values are aggregated using the Fuzzy Geometric Mean Method: where:

$$\tilde{a}_{ij} = \left(\prod_{k=1}^m a_{ij}^k \right)^{\frac{1}{m}} \tag{10}$$

After evaluating we aggregated the pairwise comparison matrix using fuzzy geometric mean method to obtain the Fuzzy weights, are shown in the following table Table 7.

Table 7. Fuzzy weights

Criteria	Fuzzy Weights
Impact of Digital Marketing	(0.263, 0.356, 0.452)
Ease of Comparison	(0.192, 0.267, 0.342)
Sufficiency of Information	(0.148, 0.208, 0.273)
Interactivity of social media	(0.118, 0.172, 0.238)
Influence on Decision-Making	(0.095, 0.137, 0.202)

The weighted normalized fuzzy decision matrix was obtained using step 5 and shown in the following table.

Table 8. Weighted normalized fuzzy decision matrix

Criteria	Travel Tickets	Local Experience Bookings	Travel Insurance
Impact of Digital Marketing	(0.132, 0.237, 0.402)	(0.058, 0.139, 0.251)	(0.175, 0.277, 0.452)
Ease of Comparison	(0.168, 0.227, 0.324)	(0.072, 0.133, 0.239)	(0.192, 0.267, 0.342)
Sufficiency of Information	(0.074, 0.139, 0.243)	(0.049, 0.115, 0.213)	(0.099, 0.161, 0.273)
Interactivity of social media	(0.079, 0.134, 0.238)	(0.026, 0.067, 0.132)	(0.079, 0.134, 0.238)
Influence on Decision-Making	(0.048, 0.091, 0.180)	(0.021, 0.053, 0.112)	(0.063, 0.107, 0.202)

Then we used step 6 to calculate Fuzzy Positive Ideal Solution (FPIS) & Fuzzy Negative Ideal Solution (FNIS)

Table 9. FPIS and FNIS

Criteria	FPIS	FNIS
Impact of Digital Marketing	(0.175, 0.277, 0.452)	(0.058, 0.139, 0.251)
Ease of Comparison	(0.192, 0.267, 0.342)	(0.072, 0.133, 0.239)
Sufficiency of Information	(0.099, 0.161, 0.273)	(0.049, 0.115, 0.213)
Interactivity of Social Media	(0.079, 0.134, 0.238)	(0.026, 0.067, 0.132)
Influence on Decision-Making	(0.063, 0.107, 0.202)	(0.021, 0.053, 0.112)

The calculation of distances from Fuzzy positive ideal solution and negative ideal solution was performed and the distances are shown below-

Table 10. Fuzzy distances from FPIS and FNIS

Alternative	Distance from FPIS	Distance from FNIS
Travel Tickets	0.874	0.523
Local Experience Bookings	0.732	0.645
Travel Insurance	0.589	0.802

In this step we find the closeness coefficient to determine the order of preference of alternatives -

Table 11. Closeness coefficients

Alternative	Closeness Coefficient	Ranks
Travel Tickets	0.374	2
Local Experience Bookings	0.468	3
Travel Insurance	0.576	1

Figure 2. Comparison of closeness coefficients w.r.to Alternatives

Figure 3. Heatmap of distances from FPIS and FNIS

4 Results and Discussion:

The **soft computing (F -TOPSIS)** method was applied to evaluate the impact of digital marketing on tourism purchases. The results show significant variations in how digital marketing influences different tourism alternatives. The Closeness Coefficients provide a clear ranking of the alternatives based on their proximity to the ideal solution ($FPIS$) and the worst-case scenario ($FNIS$).

1. Observations

- (i) Travel Insurance ranked the highest, suggesting that digital marketing has the strongest influence in this category. This may be due to targeted advertisements, trust-building content, and AI-driven policy recommendations that help consumers make decisions.
- (ii) Local Experience Bookings showed moderate influence, indicating that factors like social media campaigns, influencer marketing, and user-generated reviews play a role in consumer decision-making.
- (iii) Travel Tickets had the lowest influence from digital marketing, likely because consumers focus more on price comparison and convenience rather than advertisements.

2. Strategic Implications for Marketers

- (i) For Travel Insurance Providers: Invest more in personalized ads, AI-powered recommendations, and trust-building digital campaigns.
- (ii) For Local Experience Platforms: Focus on social media engagement, influencer collaborations, and experiential content to attract more consumers.
- (iii) For Travel Ticket Vendors: Enhance price-tracking tools and retargeting ads to maximize engagement and conversions.

5 Conclusion

This study successfully applied soft computing to evaluate the influence of digital marketing on tourism-related purchases. The findings indicate that, Travel Insurance benefits the most from digital marketing strategies due to its reliance on trust-building and personalization. Local Experience Bookings show moderate digital marketing impact, driven by social media and influencer promotions. Travel Tickets have the least influence from digital marketing, suggesting that consumers prioritize price comparison and convenience over promotional efforts.

The analysis using soft computing provided insights into the influence of digital marketing on tourism purchases. The scores values indicate the relative impact of digital marketing on different tourism alternatives:

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